

Organisational Stages and Processes of Change for Continuous Quality Improvement in Health Care

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Abstract: *The healthcare sector of any region demands continuous upgrading of the ongoing processes within these organisations. The continuous quality improvement processes in healthcare organisation include the analysis of satisfaction levels of patients, improvement in performance of healthcare professionals, cost and error reduction. The continuous quality improvement processes in the healthcare sector include proactive measures, such as the introduction of important regularity documents. These regularity documents include codes of ethics for healthcare professionals and patients, and disciplinary procedures. This study aimed to analyse stages and processes of change for continuous quality improvement in health care. This study was conducted by using the mixed methodology. The sample population of 1800 individuals was selected for quantitative phase of this study, whereas, the focus group consisting of ten research participants was considered for qualitative phase of this research. The research outcomes declared positive correlation between continuous quality improvement and patient satisfaction level. Moreover, the research outcomes also declared that standardisation of the organisational procedures and adaptability of an organisation are significant components of the process of continuous quality improvement. Improvement in the use of information technology also assists in carrying out continuous quality improvement in the healthcare sector.*

Keywords: *Continuous quality improvement, organisational stages, processes for change, quality of services, health care sector, Mauritius.*

1. Introduction

Similar to the business of other sectors, the management of healthcare organisations also strives for continuous quality improvement. The process of quality improvement in the healthcare sector needs to consider a variety of areas. The research conducted by Schembri [1] defined that quality

improvement is referred to as the utilisation of business strategies for the provision of better services to potential clients. Pursem *et al.* [2] explained quality improvement with reference to the healthcare sector. The healthcare sector of any region is dynamic in nature and demands continuous upgrading of the expertise levels of professionals along with the ongoing processes within the healthcare organisation [2]. The healthcare organisations carry out a variety of procedures for improving the quality of healthcare services. In this manner, the healthcare organisations plan to achieve short term as well as long term goals. The continuous quality improvement processes in the healthcare sector include proactive measures, such as the introduction of important regularity documents. These regularity documents include codes of ethics for healthcare professionals and patients, codes and disciplinary procedures. The research conducted by Hall, Randolph [3] stated that delays in delivery of healthcare service, failures during the provision of services incorrect billing procedures, and wrong administration of medications might be considered as the factors decreasing the quality of healthcare services. In this regard, the healthcare organisations of Mauritius plan and implement processes for change for continuous quality improvement in the healthcare sector.

The continuous quality improvement processes in healthcare organisation include the prediction of satisfaction levels of patients. In this manner, continuous quality improvement processes are also based on the performance levels of practitioners, the quality of administrator and staff performance. Wiig *et al.* [4] also stated that the quantitative (cost saving) and qualitative (error reduction) quality measures of process quality have also been found to possess positive relationships with the commitment levels of healthcare employees and control initiatives. Continuous quality improvement process also includes stages of clinical quality. The clinical quality is referred to as quality of care measured by information

related to the effectiveness of patient diagnosis and treatment. The stages of clinical quality also relate to the degree to which health care employees follow best medical practices for treating and diagnosing the service users.

The study's purpose is to identify the shortcomings of the health care sector, analyse service users' satisfaction and needs, as well as demonstrate the stages and procedures used for continuous quality improvement in the healthcare sector of Mauritius. A further purpose of this study is to explore, identify, and describe the perceptions of today's health care executives, administration executives, and health administration program managers. This research also aimed to analyse current roles and responsibilities of health administrators and the related knowledge, skills, and experiences needed to improve the quality of care.

2. Literature Review

Healthcare Sector of Mauritius

The ranking of World Health Organization declared that Mauritius possessed 84th rank with respect to quality of healthcare services [5]. Similar to other regions of the world, there is a wide range of public and private health clinics and hospitals in the region of Mauritius. The healthcare sector of Mauritius has been striving to provide quality healthcare services to their service users. On the contrary, the lack of resources and other comprehensive channels have been reducing the quality of healthcare services in this region. The major weakness of the healthcare sector of Mauritius is associated with the methods of primary care provision. The service users enter and are enrolled in the healthcare system through primary care centre; therefore, the healthcare sector of Mauritius has been analysing lacking in the primary care centres. In a similar way, the healthcare sector of Mauritius has also been developing strategies for the modernising of its healthcare sector.

Significance of Quality in Healthcare Sector

There are various definitions of quality in the healthcare sector. Sultan *et al.* [6] stated that quality of healthcare organisation depends on the rates of mortality and morbidity within an organisation. Outcome quality has also been studied in conjunction with the focus of a hospital unit. In this regard, Wiig *et al.* [4] studied the impact of operational and administrative failures and organisational learning on the quality of care in health care. The quality of care was defined regarding nurses' ability to follow best practices in the presence of supply chain and staffing limitations.

Continuous quality improvement from the perspective of health care providers includes the delivery of more accurate; evidence based, and patient centred procedure. Lifvergren and Svante [7] indicated that computer-assisted diagnosis and management can improve quality. In this

regard, the use of information technology in healthcare sector might also be considered as one of the most significant factors of continuous quality improvement processes taking place within an organisation. There are many ways to utilise information technology for providing patient-centred care. It is significant to note that health consumers need participation in their care processes. In this regard, the stages of organisational change need the active participation of employees and service users.

Stages of Continuous Quality Improvement in Healthcare Sector

The research conducted by Riskin [8] stated that there are various stages which need to be followed for improving the overall quality of services delivered through the platform of healthcare organisation. Riskin [8] stated that these stages include planning stage, quality control stage and the quality improvement stage. These three quality improvement process defined by Riskin [8] are interrelated. The planning stage is carried out to identify the forces which can contribute to improving the quality of services and products delivered through that particular platform. The quality control stage includes the utilisation of measures for assuring quality of healthcare services. On the contrary, the quality improvement stage includes the establishment of new protocols and policies for quality improvement. The research conducted by Davis [9] stated that the quality improvement at the organisational levels is not achieved by improving the quality of products and services delivered from a particular platform. However, the procedure for quality improvement also includes the area of sales, quality management in the organisational procedures and quality of personal lives of employees working in organisation.

On the other hand, the research conducted by Carayon *et al.* [10] also stated that total quality of any organisation is achieved when the product or services delivered by the platform are economical, useful, and satisfactory. Carayon *et al.* [10] presented his philosophy in some points and stated that the process of quality improvement is initiated and ended with education. The initial step of quality improvement includes the fulfilment of needs and requirements of potential consumers. Carayon *et al.* [10] also stated that the ideal state of quality improvement is based on the inspection period. He further stated that the quality improvement procedure also includes strategies for dealing with factors diminishing the quality of products or services.

On the contrary, the research conducted by Riskin [8], stated that generally, organisations consider acceptable levels of quality compromise, which might lead to increase the risk of quality compromise. The quality control program presented by Riskin [8], stated that the strategies for management commitment and the appropriate

utilisation of the equipment for quality improvement are also crucial for increasing the efficacy of the quality improvement processes. The evaluation of the cost of quality, increasing awareness of quality, the intake of system corrective actions, and the use of zero effect programs are also considered as some of the factors contributing to the process of quality improvement [8]. Riskin [8] also stated that zero effect programs are followed by training monitoring and setting of zero defects, which contribute in the removal of errors, the provision of recognition, and the implementation of quality tips. The quality improvement procedure demonstrated by Riskin [8] can be considered as the cycle, such that the entire process can be repeated for carrying out further improvement in quality.

Davis [9] also exposed a quality model consisting of the combination of interpersonal and technical quality components along with the potential impact of these quality components on the public and private health sector. Davis [9] also explained that quality is the property which might have a significant impact on health and well-being of potential service users. For this reason, quality in healthcare services can be broadly categorised into various factors. These factors include the relationship between quality assessment and evaluation of programs by considering their technical and interpersonal components [9]. Moreover, the concepts accessibility, continuity, and the coordination with the implication content might also contribute to achieving satisfaction patients and professionals. In this regard, the concept of continuous quality improvement is health care also involve necessary measures to improve the satisfaction levels of employees.

Continuous Quality Improvement Process

The research conducted by Wiig *et al.* [4] stated that changes are implemented in any organisation with the intention of continuous quality improvement. Changes in any organisation are not only limited to the introduction of information technology [4]. For this reason, some of the current organisations have been implementing the strategies for continuous quality improvements within the organisation. Most of the organisations utilise the Plan, Do, Check, and Act (PDCA) cycle for improving Total Quality Improvement processes. On the other hand, some of the authors also believe that continuous quality improvement can only be achieved through systematic planning, control, and monitoring. Figure 1 represent some important steps of continuous quality improvement process, which are followed by a variety of healthcare organisations.

Wiig *et al.* [4] demonstrated five essential elements for continuous quality improvements. He demonstrated that clients are centre to any organisation. Moreover, process management, the involvement of people, the mastery of innovation processes, and leadership levels also contribute

to processes for continuous quality improvements. On the other hand, the research conducted by Obermeyer *et al.* [11] also discussed the importance of involvement of people for continuous quality improvement. It is also argued that the involvement of employees also include training of employees and motivating them to become part of change process.

Figure 1: Process of Continuous Quality Improvement
(Source: Glibert, 2017)

The human resource department of any organisation implements coherent philosophies and practices for organisational management. Continuous quality improvement within organisation also requires the involvement of professionals in the educational systems for changing the ways of thinking and acting within the organisation [11]. A wide majority of the employer organisations only believes in training their employees, despite educating them. In this regard, professional training along with the education session is anticipated to assist in the analysis of needs of the employees. The theoretical, as well as practical training, is also anticipated to assist in the evaluation of results (observations and change of behaviours). In this regard, the involvement of employees in planning and implementation of quality improvement processes also contributes in the process of continuous quality improvement [11].

The involvement of employees in the process of quality improvements also encourages employees to work beyond their level of knowledge; however, it is crucial to motivating employees to become active part of the processes for continuous quality improvement. The behaviour of employees can be considered as one of the

most significant factors for involvement of employees within the processes of change within the organisations. The research conducted by Wright *et al.* [4] stated that organisations need to focus using the external or internal stimuli for shaping the behaviour of employees. Moreover, the organisations might also take necessary measures for motivating employees towards certain aim and objectives. In the final stage, the organisational management implement strategies to fulfil needs and desires of employees [4].

In this regard, it can be stated that professionals development of nursing is affected by the management and procedures implemented within the healthcare organisation or vice versa. The research conducted by Wiig *et al.* [4] also stated that organisations possessing mutual expectations in their psychological contract consider their employees as part of organisation. These organisations respect opinions of their employees and value their concerns for achieving continuous quality improvement.

3. Ethical Clearance

This study was performed after receiving ethical approval from the Institutional Review Board.

4. Methodology

This research was conducted by using mixed methodology which incorporates the advantages of questionnaires and the interview analysis. The methodological triangulation blended qualitative and quantitative analysis for the provision of abundant and robust data reliability. Creswell [12] stated that the examination of primary and secondary information also enhances the trustworthiness of research findings. The researcher used quantitative approach for the identification of numerical data interpreted by using the statistical methods [12]. Moser and Kalton [13] also stated that quantitative research has been recognised as the reliable mode of inquiry, as compared to other methods. On the contrary, the qualitative research allows researchers in analysing views, narrations, and perspectives of administrators and patients. Moreover, in qualitative research, it is easier to maintain anonymity, confidentiality, and privacy of the research participants.

Research Hypotheses

Following hypotheses were considered by the researcher:

H₁: There is no difference between the patients' satisfaction and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H₂: There is no difference between the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

H₃: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Data Collection Tool

In this research, data collection was performed by using quantitative surveys and semi-structured interviews. Creswell [14] stated that the use of close ended questionnaire can be considered as the principal method of data collection. The data collection in this research was performed through survey questionnaire and semi-structured interviews. The use of data collection instrument also assists in collecting data from a large cohort of population, allowing easy analysis of research outcomes. Questionnaire for this research was designed by considering 5 points Likert scale ranging from strongly agrees to strongly disagree. The survey questionnaire for this research was based on the indicators representing the concepts related to the participation of the patient in his own care.

On the other hand, the tool of interview session is also considered as most comprehensive tool for collecting descriptive data and information [12]. The interview sessions are most suitable for acquiring the responses, experiences, and perceptions of the research participants. Most of these interviews are in verbal and contextual form, such that these interviews are subjective to inadequacies and errors which perform descriptive detailing process. The questionnaire which was used as the data collection tool in this research was self-administered and the cover letter was provided to each of the research participants which explained aim and objective of the research.

Creswell [14] argued that the semi-structured interview sessions summarise qualitative methodology, which questions the observations of respondents on the basis of individual experiences. Similarly, the research conducted by McNabb [15] declared that the use of open-ended questions in qualitative research allows researchers in exploring deep concept and knowledge about a particular process. However, considering the context of aims and objectives of research, semi-structured interviews were most suitable for this research.

Settings and Population Sample

This research was carried out in the Republic of Mauritius. In the year 2014, approximately 1,072,205 patients were facilitated as outpatients in the government hospitals and a considerable majority of population rely on the government hospitals [16]. The Ministry of Health [16] mentioned that there are approximately 8700 healthcare professionals across the entire country. The definition provided by WHO mentioned that Medical doctors, nurses, midwifery professionals, dentists, and pharmacists are included among healthcare professionals.

Initially the researchers searched for the healthcare organisations with at least 100 beds; however, some of the hospitals were found more appropriate to be included in this research. AG Jeetoo Hospital, Apollo Bramwell,

Victoria in Quatres Borne, and Sir Seewoosagur Ramgoolam National Hospital were thus included. The sample population for this research included healthcare executives, board members, and health administration managers. Similar to healthcare professionals working in selected health care institutes. Researcher also included patients visiting the selected healthcare organisations.

The sample size for this research was calculated by using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), such that the sample size was calculated by considering the effect size at 0.10, power at 0.80, and the alpha set at 0.05. On the contrary, the reliability for Cronbach's alpha was approximately 0.63 to 0.84. Stratified sampling was performed for selecting approximately 1800 research participants for quantitative research. On the other hand, purposive sampling was carried out for selecting ten research participants for qualitative research.

Bonett and Wright [17] stated that purposive sampling method is useful for performing exploratory qualitative research. Yuskel [18] stated that theoretical purposeful sampling assists in the joint collection of theory and the analysis of data for the generation of theory. For this reason, the qualitative phase of this research considered purposeful sampling because of its efficacy. On the other hand, stratified random sample can be considered as the most appropriate sampling technique for highlighting a specific subgroup within a population. Tipton *et al.* [19] stated that stratified sampling assures the presence of subgroup within the population sample.

Interview sessions for this research were conducted in the focus group setting, such that the respondents were allowed to discuss their perceptions, views, and ideas about the healthcare system in Mauritius.

5. Results and Findings

Variables

The dependent variable considered in this research was overall quality of health care administration services rating, whereas, independent variables for this research include stages and processes for continuous quality improvement within the organisation. The independent variable is further categorised into patient satisfaction levels, the ISO management standards for health service management and the adaptability of an organisation to the revolution requirements.

Variables included in this research were given initials in order to make it easy to put in statistical software.

Table 1: Dependent and Independent Variables

Dependent Variable	
1.	Overall Quality of Health Care (QHC)
Independent Variable	
1.	Patients' Satisfactions (PS)
2.	ISO Quality Standards Compliance (ISO)

3.	Adaptability (Adap)
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Quantitative Phase

Approximately 1811 close-ended questionnaires were received by the researcher after completion. The SPSS software was used for performing statistical analysis of the data collected through the questionnaire survey. T-test was performed of comparing mean differences between the dimensions of questionnaire with the score of positive response. Moreover, Pearson correlation was performed to examine the relationship between independent and dependent variable. The reliability of survey instrument was found by using Cronbach's alpha.

Reliability. Table 2 represented reliability statistics of this research.

Table 2: Reliability Statistics

Scale: ALL VARIABLES

Case Processing Summary

		N	percent
Cases	Valid	1800	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0.0	0.0
	Total	1800	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
0.63	67

This scale was used to measure whether the questions included in the survey are all reliable, having similar latent variables. The Cronbach's value for this research was 0.63, presenting reliability of the questionnaire survey.

T-test. T test were perform to analyse statistical significance between the considered dependent and independent variables.

QHC in comparison to PS

We hypothesised that;

H₁: There is no difference between the patients' satisfaction and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 3: Paired Sample Statistics for QHC and PS

Paired Samples Statistics				
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean

QHC	3.00	1800	0.43	0.01
PS	3.03	1800	0.44	0.01

Table 3 represented the mean for the QHC and PS was 3.00 and 3.03 respectively. The standard deviation for the QHC is 0.43, whereas, standard deviation for PS was 0.44.

Table 4: Paired Sample Tests for QHC and PS

	Paired Differences				Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		
			Lower	Upper	
QHC PS	-0.03	0.62	-0.06	0.0002	0.052

The statistical outcomes stated the presence of statistically significant relation between the QHC and PS. Mean number for patient satisfaction was equal to the mean for the quality of health care. In this regard, participants demonstrating preference for PS were found to experienced better quality of care.

QHC in comparison ISO

H₂: There is no difference between the ISO compliance and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 5: Paired Sample Statistics for QHC and ISO Compliance

Paired Samples Statistics				
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QHC	3.00	1800	0.43	0.01
ISO	3.00	1800	0.45	0.01

	Paired Differences				Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		
			Lower	Upper	
QHC Adapt	-0.01	0.69	-0.038	0.038	0.030

The paired sample statistics presented in table 5 demonstrated mean values for QHC was 3.00, whereas; mean value for the PS was 3.00. The standard deviation for the QHC and ISO were 0.43 and 0.45.

Table 6: Paired Sample Tests for QHC and ISO Compliance

	Paired Differences				Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Dev.	95 percent Confidence Interval of the Difference		
			Lower	Upper	
QHC - ISO	-0.01	0.63	-0.04	0.02	0.05

Table 6 represented that mean number for ISO compliance was less than the mean for the quality of health care. The differences between means represent statistically significant difference between QHC and ISO. The statistical analysis revealed that research participant who showed preference for ISO compliance principally experience better quality of care.

QHC in comparison Adaptability

H₃: There is no difference between adaptability and overall quality of health care in health care system in Mauritius.

Table 7: Paired Sample Statistics for QHC and Adaptability

Paired Samples Statistics				
	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
QHC	3.00	1800	0.43	0.01
Adap	3.00	1800	0.54	0.01

Table 7 presented mean values for QHC and Adap were 3.00 and 3.00. The standard deviation for the QHC was 0.43 and for adaptability mean value was 0.54.

Table 8: Paired Sample Tests for QHC and Adaptability

Table 8 revealed that mean number for adaptability was less than the mean for the quality of health care. In this regard, participants who showed preference for adaptability principally experience better quality of care.

Qualitative Phase

The qualitative data acquired in this research was analysed by using thematic analysis. Yüksel, [18] stated that thematic analysis is a method used for recognising, evaluating, and reporting patterns of the collected information. Rubin and Babbie [20] stated that the use of thematic analysis in a qualitative study determines clear links between the objectives of the research and the findings of the raw data.

The responses of research participants declared that health care technologies and innovations assure continuous quality improvement in healthcare sector. Moreover, technological inventories were always considered the only feasible way to approach modern medicine services and systems in many underserved scenarios, notably those of the rural areas of developing countries. My interview with the director of the managers, health care employees and other leaders in health administration exemplifies;

“the innovative use of health care technology would be different in different place and different situation. It does not have any standard definition. Different country has different infrastructure according to their economic condition, manpower and geographical structure. If anybody uses ISO for medical care whether it is store-forward or real time; in that sense we are doing telemedicine in Mauritius.”

The internal information and communication infrastructure in healthcare sector of Mauritius is still very basic; therefore, acquiring healthcare services is still long term procedure. The findings of previously published literature revealed that the implementation of the International Organisation for Standardization (ISO) assists in diminishing health related problems. The healthcare organisation needs to be efficient enough to effectively use information technology within the healthcare sector. Its utilisation can also be considered as bringing innovation in the healthcare sector.

In response to a question related to the use of technology for continuous quality improvement, the administrative manager stated;

“.....we just have started to work in this field and we have plan about EHR but it is true that, we don't have enough workforce yet regarding telemedicine and e-health. Awareness about this matter is very much important among the health personnel as well as the patients.....private health sector can also take initiatives concerning this issue, as 60 percent of patients take health care services from private clinics and hospitals in Mauritius....”

The satisfaction levels of patients might also be enhanced due to innovation in healthcare services; however, lack of innovation in laboratory diagnosis in Mauritius has been considered as a challenging situation for the healthcare sector. Some of the renowned healthcare organisations, clinics and consultation centres were considered for this

research. One of the respondent working in healthcare sector was interrogated about the effectiveness of innovation for continuous quality improvement in healthcare sector. The responses of research participants declared that the standardisation of the routine procedure implemented in the healthcare system is anticipated to assist in continuous quality improvement within the healthcare organisation. Respondents also declared that standardisation of common procedures taking place within an organisation is anticipated to assist in acquiring improved functionality, improvement in the information provision, and improved communication between healthcare professionals working in the healthcare organisation.

The interviewee responded that that;

“When a patient comes here for follow-up, his cardiac operation is done in last year, patient becomes very pleased by the response of consultant. It is because of database; health care professionals are maintaining their patient's database (EHR). Whenever a patient comes for follow-up, health care professional can have all record by EHR very easily and quickly. Patients are satisfied because health care professionals are concerned about them. Our medical specialists are enough qualified but we don't have enough ICT culture among health personnel. There are other constrains such as high price of bandwidth and interrupted power supply.”

The responses of research participants also declared strong link between patient satisfaction and continuous quality improvement in health care delivery system. Patients and their immediate family members expect to be satisfied with the services delivered by health care institutions. One of the responded declared that;

“Patients' satisfaction is based on affordable fee, promptness of attention, good staff attitude, respect for patients and their rights, providing privacy and confidentiality, providing adequate information, availability of drugs and logistics and above all a healthy and clean environment”

Respondents were also interrogated about the factors which might hinder continuous quality improvement within the healthcare sector. The responses of research participants declared that there are various factors which limit the effectiveness of the quality improvement processes. The respondents highlighted factors limiting continuous quality improvement in healthcare organisation. The Human Resources Manager replied;

“The programs rule us”. Not 10 as we don't get the full functionality that we need or could get - because insufficient funding. Hence we don't see end game achieved.”

Manager Patient Safety and Quality stated;

“Skills mismatch as left. Also issue of difficulty of time poor staff having to interact with sluggish systems. Sense

of IT systems replacing (not in a good way) skilled staff in some situations. Skill mix/experience in decision makers not ideal”

Clinical Service Manager demonstrated;

“Some systems don't talk to each other. Current HR system not very good. "Don't tell us what we want to know" - end result is arguing over correctness vs. the problems. Inaccuracy/inconsistency over data entry. Small data entry errors can extrapolate to thousands of dollars' worth of errors in terms of revenue/expenditure”

Human Resources Manager notified;

“Still not enough buy in system use/benefits - need to win over biggest naysayers. There is inadequate training and support for system use. There is prioritisation of functionality provided because of cost and other trade-offs. Too much reliance still on human entry and hence subsequent errors.”

Manager of Performance and Activity said;

“Only sufficient resources for this to be done on an ad hoc basis Due to turnover in middle management, training and awareness issues.... The work environment does not mirror the home environment for example; clunkiness of systems; lack of support for work processes..”

Clinical Service Manager added;

“Need more personalised information provision / presentation and faster responsiveness in meeting their information needs ... need more consolidation / transformation of data to information and easy to use reporting tools.”

Continuous quality improvement in healthcare sector of any organisation is also dependent on the levels of expertise of healthcare professionals. Trained professionals carry out high quality routine procedures, resulting in increasing satisfaction levels of patients. In a similar manner, the availability and accessibility towards health services also increase the satisfaction levels of patients. One of the respondents from my interviewee mentioned;

“It is really a good step for rural people and patients can have specialised consultancy from faraway from main city. But we don't have enough setup to diagnose the patients so; ultimately we have to send the patients to capital city for ECG, MRI, and CT scan and others even for digital X-ray”

The healthcare organisations need to upgrade their systems and knowledge according to the standards. The standardisation of the healthcare services is anticipated to assist in reducing ambiguities and complications caused as a result of poor utilisation of skills, problems related to the speed of response of systems, and insufficient funding for systems. The research participants were asked what ways could be utilised for improving quality of healthcare services.

Manager Patient Safety and Quality stated;

“Moving from paper has been a good thing. More user friendly systems-access, workflow support, navigability, and personalisation.”

Similarly, the general Manager notified;

“Technologies are only providing an enhancing function - making information more immediate and electronic.”

6. Discussion

This research was conducted to analyse stages and strategies of quality improvement in the healthcare sector. This research was conducted by considering three factors which could impact the process of continuous quality improvement. These three factors include patient satisfaction level, the ISO standards, and the adaptability of healthcare organisation.

The patients admitted in small community hospitals do not possess high expectancies; therefore, needs of these patients are most often satisfied with the quality of health services [21]. On the other hand, patients hospitalised in teaching hospital might possess complex care needs. The research conducted by Harkin et al. [22] stated that due to complex needs of care, the satisfaction levels of sick patients admitted in teaching hospitals are extremely high. Outcomes of the research conducted by Harkin et al. [22] demonstrated that the academic status of healthcare providers might have positive influence on patients' expectations of service and care [22]. At this stage, the analysis of the relationship between patient satisfaction and hospital statuses remained a complex issue which needs further research in both the teaching and nonteaching environment.

In this regards, the feedbacks acquired from patients are extremely essential for analysing the overall performance of healthcare organisation. Analysis of expectations and perceptions of patients' also health care professionals in acknowledging factors related to users' satisfaction. Outcomes acquired from this research could be used by managers to introduce more measures related to quality performance. The use of ISO standards contributes in well-functioning quality system. Improvement in the quality of healthcare services is an integral part of a total quality system. The utilisation of ISO standards also includes satisfaction of customers [23]. Healthcare services cannot only be considered as actions and behaviours within healthcare organisation; rather, continuous quality improvement in the healthcare sector is based on the ways in which patients and service users perceive and interpret those actions. The ISO 9001 standard consists of various factors which need to be considered by the healthcare organisations for continuous quality improvement. These standards include effective communication with patients; care for patient property; accurate analysis of patients' requirement and expectation. In the light of research outcomes, the implementation of ISO standards is

anticipated to have a significant impact on continuous quality improvement. Health care in Mauritius has been struggling for implementing diverse changes in patterns of care services delivered to service users. Currently practised protocols and procedures must be adapted to health insurance programs. Moreover, the healthcare sector of Mauritius has been improving the use of technology in the healthcare sector.

7. Conclusion

Health care operations need to be continuously improved with respect to significantly changing demand of healthcare. The process of continuous quality improvement in healthcare organisation consisted of various stages and processes. Healthcare professionals are considered as responsible for bringing improvements in the entire healthcare system. For this reason, the inclusion of employees during the establishment and implementation of quality improvement processes can be considered as one of the most significant factors affecting quality improvement processes. This research was conducted by analysing the perceptions acquired from health care professionals working at different organisational level and patients visiting healthcare organisations. Considering the perceptions acquired from research participants, it can be concluded that reduction of cost of healthcare services, introduction of technology, and the standardisation of procedures ensure continuous quality improvement in healthcare organisations. The improved information technology management tends to improve efficiency and quality of healthcare. Research outcomes also declared that effective inventory management and supply chain management also positively affect the efficiency and performance of the hospitals in the health care sector. Moreover, the adaptability of an organisation to implement innovations also has a significant impact on quality of services delivered by healthcare organisations.

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9. Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that no conflict of interest exists.

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